

Supplementary Table 1. Summary statistics for cortisol-associated SNPs using as instrumental variables

SNP	Chr	nearby gene	EAF	Position	EA	OA	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	F-statistic
rs11621961	14	SERPINA6	0.36	94769476	T	C	-0.08	0.01	4.0×10^{-8}	30.2
rs12589136	14	SERPINA6	0.22	94793686	T	G	0.10	0.01	3.3×10^{-12}	48.6
rs2749527	14	SERPINA1	0.49	94827068	T	C	-0.08	0.01	5.2×10^{-11}	43.2

Abbreviations: SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; Chr, chromosome; EAF, effect allele frequency; EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; SE, standard error; P, p value; GWAS, genome-wide association study.

^{a)} Beta coefficients represent the SD change in plasma cortisol concentrations per additional effect allele.

Instrumental variables were selected from CORNET consortium (Bolton JL, et al. **PLOS Genetics**. 2014; 10(7): e10004474.

Supplementary Table 2. Data sources used for the MR analysis

	Traits	Sample size	Population	Consortium or cohort study (Link URL)
Exposure	Plasma cortisol	12,597	European	CORNET(28) (https://datashare.is.ed.ac.uk/handle/10283/2787)*
Exposure (validation)	Plasma cortisol	25,314	European	CORNET(22) (https://datashare.ed.ac.uk/handle/10283/3836)
Outcome	Grip strength	461,026	European	UK Biobank (MRC IEU) (29) (https://doi.org/10.5523/bris.2fahpksont1zi26xosyamqo8rr)*
	WBLM	454,850		
	ALM	450,243	European	Pei YF, et al. (30)*
Using for multivariable MR and MR-BMA analyses	Fasting glucose	58,074	European	MAGIC (31) (https://magicinvestigators.org)*
	Fasting insulin	51,750		
	HOMA-IR	37,037		
	BMI	461,460	European	UK Biobank (MRC IEU) (29) (https://doi.org/10.5523/bris.2fahpksont1zi26xosyamqo8rr)*
	Waist circumference	462,166	Mixed	GLGC (32) (http://csg.sph.umich.edu/willer/public/lipids2013/)*
	Triglycerides	177,861		
Outcome for sex stratified analysis	HDL cholesterol	187,167		
	Grip strength Men	166,424	European	UK Biobank (Neale Lab) (33) (http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank)
	Grip strength Women	193,280	European	
	WBLM Men	163,815	European	
	WBLM Women	190,993	European	
	ALM Men	205,513	European	Pei YF, et al. (30)*
ALM Women	244,730			

*, Summary results were obtained through the MR-Base platform (database version v3.0.0 -2020-09-02) (34).

Abbreviations: MR, Mendelian randomization; BMA, Bayesian model averaging; CORNET, Cortisol Network; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM, appendicular lean mass; BMI, body mass index; MRC-IEU, MRC Integrative Epidemiology Unit; HOMA-IR, homeostasis model assessment for insulin resistance; MAGIC, the Meta-Analyses of Glucose and Insulin-related traits Consortium; HDL cholesterol, high density lipoprotein cholesterol; GLGC, The Global Lipids Genetics

Supplementary Table 3. Summary statistics for association of instrumental variables with muscle strength and mass

SNP	EA	OA	Grip strength			WBLM			ALM		
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P
rs11621961	T	C	0.0023	0.0015	0.13	0.0034	0.0013	0.0069	0.0042	0.0020	0.033
rs12589136	T	G	-0.0032	0.0018	0.082	-0.0024	0.0015	0.11	-0.0016	0.0023	0.50
rs2749527	T	C	0.0027	0.0015	0.068	0.0025	0.0012	0.045	0.0024	0.0019	0.20

Abbreviations: SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM, appendicular lean mass; SE, standard error, P, p value.

^{a)} Beta coefficients represent the SD change in each outcome per additional effect allele.

Supplementary Table 4.

Summary statistics for association of instrumental variables with muscle strength and mass in men and women

SNP	EA	OA	Grip strength						WBLM					
			MEN			Women			MEN			Women		
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P
rs11621961	T	C	7×10^{-4}	0.003	0.85	0.002	0.003	0.47	-3×10^{-4}	0.004	0.94	0.012	0.003	4×10^{-4}
rs12589136	T	G	-0.004	0.004	0.37	-0.004	0.004	0.23	-0.002	0.004	0.61	-0.004	0.004	0.26
rs2749527	T	C	0.002	0.003	0.66	0.007	0.003	0.01	-0.001	0.003	0.71	0.008	0.003	0.01
SNP	EA	OA	ALM											
			MEN			Women								
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P						
rs11621961	T	C	5×10^{-4}	0.003	0.72	0.007	0.003	0.02						
rs12589136	T	G	-0.002	0.004	0.60	-0.001	0.003	0.73						
rs2749527	T	C	6×10^{-5}	0.003	0.79	0.004	0.003	0.07						

Abbreviations: SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM; appendicular lean mass; EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; SE, standard error, P, p value

^{a)} Beta coefficients represent the SD change in each outcome per additional effect allele.

Supplementary Table 5. Summary statistics for association of instrumental variables with traits using for multivariable MR

SNP	EA	OA	Fasting glucose			Fasting insulin			HOMA-IR		
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P
rs11621961	T	C	-0.0016	0.0035	0.64	0.0024	0.0035	0.50	0.001	0.0046	0.76
rs12589136	T	G	3×10^{-4}	0.0038	0.93	6×10^{-4}	0.0038	0.88	0.024	0.0048	0.62
rs2749527	T	C	-9×10^{-4}	0.0031	0.78	-0.0015	0.0032	0.64	0.001	0.0040	0.86
SNP	EA	OA	BMI			Waist circumference			Triglycerides		
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P
rs11621961	T	C	-0.0014	0.0020	0.50	-2×10^{-5}	0.0018	0.99	-0.008	0.0051	0.28
rs12589136	T	G	-0.0024	0.0024	0.33	-0.003	0.0022	0.80	0.003	0.0057	0.89
rs2749527	T	C	-0.0013	0.0019	0.50	5×10^{-4}	0.0018	0.42	7×10^{-4}	0.0046	0.62
SNP	EA	OA	HDL cholesterol								
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P						
rs11621961	T	C	0.0072	0.0053	0.18						
rs12589136	T	G	0.0011	0.0058	0.66						
rs2749527	T	C	0.0001	0.0048	0.93						

Abbreviations: SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; SE, standard error, P, p value; HOMA-IR, homeostasis model assessment for insulin resistance; BMI, Body mass index; HDL cholesterol, high density lipoprotein cholesterol.

^{a)} Beta coefficients represent the SD change in each outcome per additional effect allele.

Supplementary Table 6. Summary statistics for cortisol-associated SNPs from extended cortisol GWAS

SNP	Chr	nearby gene	EAF	Position	EA	OA	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	F-statistic
rs9989237	14	SERPINA6	0.21	94328865	T	C	0.09	0.01	2.2×10^{-19}	81.2
rs2736898	14	SERPINA1	0.50	94823817	T	C	0.06	0.01	7.0×10^{-14}	56.1
rs11620763	14	SERPINA6	0.19	94302005	A	G	-0.08	0.01	2.0×10^{-10}	40.5
rs7146221	14	SERPINA6	0.45	94302744	A	G	-0.05	0.01	6.3×10^{-10}	38.3

Abbreviations: SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; Chr, chromosome; EAF, effect allele frequency; EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; SE, standard error; P, p value; GWAS, genome-wide association study.

^{a)} Beta coefficients represent the SD change in plasma cortisol concentrations per additional effect allele.

Instrumental variables were selected from CORNET consortium (Andrew AC, et al. **Journal of Human Genetics**. 2021; 66:625-636.)

Supplementary Table 7.

Summary statistics for association of instrumental variables from extended cortisol GWAS with muscle strength and mass

SNP	EA	OA	Grip strength			WBLM			ALM		
			Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P	Beta ^{a)}	SE	P
rs9989237	T	C	-0.0030	0.0018	0.100	-0.0024	0.0015	0.120	-0.0016	0.0023	0.500
rs2736898	T	C	-0.0027	0.0015	0.070	-0.0025	0.0012	0.045	-0.0024	0.0019	0.206
rs11620763	A	G	0.0044	0.0018	0.018	0.0018	0.0015	0.240	-0.0016	0.0024	0.503
rs7146221	A	G	0.0017	0.0015	0.250	0.0026	0.0013	0.036	0.0027	0.0019	0.155

Abbreviations: SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM, appendicular lean mass; SE, standard error, P, p value.

^{a)} Beta coefficients represent the SD change in each outcome per additional effect allele.

Instrumental variables were selected from CORNET consortium (Andrew AC, et al. **Journal of Human Genetics**. 2021; 66:625-636.)

Supplementary Table 8. The correlation matrix between genetic variants

Original cortisol GWAS ^{a)}				
	rs11621961_T_C	rs12589136_T_G	rs2749527_C_T	
rs11621961_T_C	1	-0.233301	-0.437229	
rs12589136_T_G	-0.233301	1	0.491219	
rs2749527_C_T	-0.437229	0.491219	1	
Extended cortisol GWAS ^{b)}				
	rs9989237_T_C	rs2736898_T_C	rs11620763_A_G	rs7146221_A_G
rs9989237_T_C	1	0.493006	-0.182103	-0.189644
rs2736898_T_C	0.493006	1	-0.217721	-0.371343
rs11620763_A_G	-0.182103	-0.217721	1	0.524575
rs7146221_A_G	-0.189644	-0.371343	0.524575	1

Abbreviations: GWAS, genome-wide association study.

a) Bolton JL, et al. **PLOS Genetics**. 2014; 10(7): e10004474; b) Andrew AC, et al. **Journal of Human Genetics**. 2021; 66:625-636.

Supplementary Table 9. MR analysis for association of cortisol with muscle strength and mass

Method	Grip strength			WBLM			ALM		
	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P
IVW	-0.032	-0.044 ~ -0.020	3e-04	-0.032	-0.046 ~ -0.017	0.004	-0.031	-0.049 ~ -0.012	0.001
Cochran's Q	1.252		0.535	0.009		0.996	1.712		0.425
Weighted-median	-0.031	-0.056 ~ -0.006	0.015	-0.029	-0.051 ~ -0.007	0.009	-0.027	-0.059 ~ -0.004	0.017
MR-Egger	-0.028	-0.195 ~ 0.138	0.794	0.029	-0.111 ~ 0.169	0.754	0.079	-0.133 ~ 0.291	0.599
MR-Egger intercept	-3e-04		0.978	-0.005		0.546	-0.009		0.492

Abbreviations: MR, Mendelian randomization; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM, appendicular lean mass; 95%CI, 95% confidence interval; P, p value; IVW, inverse variance weighted

Note: a) Estimates represent the SD change in each outcome per SD increases in plasma cortisol concentrations. b) We used fixed-effect IVW analysis accounting for genetic correlation between variants. In the IVW analysis, differences were considered statistically significant at P-value < 0.05. In the weighted-median analysis, associations with P-value below 0.017 (where P = 0.05/3) were deemed statistically significant, and P-value between 0.017 and 0.05 were regarded as suggestive evidence of associations.

Supplementary Table 10. MR analysis for association of cortisol with muscle strength and mass in men and women

Men									
Method	Grip strength			WBLM			ALM		
	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P
IVW	-0.021	-0.054 ~ 0.011	0.192	-0.001	-0.032 ~ 0.034	0.968	-0.008	-0.035 ~ 0.019	0.564
Cochran's Q	0.273		0.872	0.352		0.839	0.129		0.938
Weighted-median	-0.020	-0.074 ~ 0.034	0.474	-0.003	-0.055 ~ 0.060	0.927	-0.007	-0.053 ~ 0.039	0.766
MR-Egger	-0.109	-0.483 ~ 0.265	0.670	-0.108	-0.491 ~ 0.275	0.679	-0.063	-0.381 ~ 0.256	0.766
MR-Egger intercept	0.008		0.725	0.009		0.680	0.005		0.795
Women									
Method	Grip strength			WBLM			ALM		
	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P
IVW	-0.061	-0.090 ~ -0.031	2e-05	-0.092	-0.122 ~ -0.061	6e-05	-0.049	-0.074 ~ -0.025	8e-05
Cochran's Q	0.887		0.642	4.643		0.098	4.109		0.128

Weighted- median	-0.044	-0.101 ~ 0.012	0.120	-0.084	-0.143 ~ -0.024	0.006	-0.045	-0.092 ~ 0.001	0.055
MR-Egger	-0.021	-0.425 ~ 0.384	0.936	0.233	-0.123 ~ 0.590	0.422	0.198	-0.089 ~ 0.485	0.406
MR-Egger intercept	-0.003		0.892	-0.028		0.323	-0.021		0.338

Abbreviations: MR, Mendelian randomization; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM, appendicular lean mass; 95%CI, 95% confidence interval; P, p value; IVW, inverse variance weighted

Note: a) Estimates represent the SD change in each outcome per SD increases in plasma cortisol concentrations. b) We used fixed-effect IVW analysis accounting for genetic correlation between variants. In the IVW analysis, differences were considered statistically significant at P-value < 0.05. In the weighted-median analysis, associations with P-value below 0.017 (where $P = 0.05/3$) were deemed statistically significant, and P-value between 0.017 and 0.05 were regarded as suggestive evidence of associations.

Supplementary Table 11. Multivariable MR analysis for association of cortisol with grip strength and WBLM (adjusted for two potential contributing factors)

Grip strength				WBLM			
	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P		Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P
Adjusted for glucose and insulin	-0.008	-0.204 ~ 0.188	0.936	Adjusted for glucose and insulin	-0.043	-0.278 ~ 0.192	0.721
Adjusted for glucose and BMI	-0.016	-0.043 ~ 0.039	0.565	Adjusted for glucose and BMI	-0.035	-0.100 ~ 0.030	0.300
Adjusted for glucose and triglycerides	-0.019	-0.046 ~ 0.008	0.174	Adjusted for glucose and triglycerides	-0.031	-0.064 ~ 0.002	0.065
Adjusted for insulin and BMI	-0.029	-0.043 ~ -0.015	1e-05*	Adjusted for insulin and BMI	-0.032	-0.048 ~ -0.016	3e-05*
Adjusted for insulin and triglycerides	-0.028	-0.048 ~ -0.008	0.003*	Adjusted for insulin and triglycerides	-0.032	-0.054 ~ -0.010	0.004*
Adjusted for BMI and triglycerides	-0.027	-0.045 ~ -0.009	0.003*	Adjusted for BMI and triglycerides	-0.032	-0.054 ~ -0.010	0.002*

Abbreviations: MR, Mendelian randomization; WBLM, whole body lean mass; CI, confidence interval; P, p value; BMI, body mass index.

Note: a) Estimates represent the SD change in each outcome per SD increases in plasma cortisol concentrations. Multivariable MR analysis was performed using fixed-effect inverse-variance weighted method accounting for genetic correlations between variants. *, P-value < 0.05.

Supplementary Table 12. MR analysis for association of cortisol with muscle strength and mass using extended cortisol GWAS

Method	Grip strength			WBLM			ALM		
	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P	Estimate ^{a)}	95%CI	P
IVW	-0.043	-0.075 ~ -0.012	0.007	-0.028	-0.054 ~ -0.001	0.039	-0.008	-0.048 ~ 0.032	0.696
Cochran's Q	0.800		0.850	2.274		0.518	5.382		0.146
Weighted-median	-0.042	-0.069 ~ -0.015	0.002	-0.029	-0.054 ~ -0.004	0.022	-0.022	-0.058 ~ 0.014	0.237
MR-Egger	-0.049	-0.152 ~ 0.053	0.447	0.015	-0.071 ~ 0.101	0.766	0.078	-0.053 ~ 0.209	0.365
MR-Egger intercept	4e-04		0.903	-0.003		0.379	-0.006		0.278

Abbreviations: MR, Mendelian randomization; GWAS, genome wide association study; WBLM, whole body lean mass; ALM, appendicular lean mass; 95%CI, 95% confidence interval; P, p value; IVW, inverse variance weighted

Note: a) Estimates represent the SD change in each outcome per SD increases in plasma cortisol concentrations. b) We used fixed-effect IVW analysis accounting for genetic correlation between variants. In the IVW analysis, differences were considered statistically significant at P-value < 0.05. In the weighted-median analysis, associations with P-value below 0.017 (where $P = 0.05/3$) were deemed statistically significant, and P-value between 0.017 and 0.05 were regarded as suggestive evidence of associations.